

WAR: WHY ATTACK MEME COINS?

THE NIGERIAN SECURITIES AND EXCHANGE COMMISSION'S ROLE IN BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY & CRYPTOCURRENCY INVESTMENTS

A PRESENTATION BY SHARON OKEREKE AND CHIDERA NNAJI

BACKGROUND OF THE WAR

Blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies have in the last decade recorded a very high level of participation, investment and utilisation especially amongst the country's tech-savvy and pro-blockchain youth population, who are eager to adopt digital assets. It is believed that whilst some utilise it for just investment, others use it to move funds and investments in an untraceable manner.

Upon its introduction into the Nigerian financial market space, it has over time received major confrontation from the Nigerian Government through its financial regulatory frontiers the Central Bank of Nigeria ("CBN") and the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission ("SEC, Nigeria" or "Nigerian SEC").

Whilst the activities of CBN may not be said to have been directly affected by the then novel Blockchain Investment, like the SEC was affected, the CBN eventually came to see a huge mist cover its monitoring eyes on the total money in circulation hence it released a circular in February 2021, distancing the Financial Market from Crypto and prohibiting banks from engaging in Crypto transactions.

THE BEGINNING OF THE WAR

Increasing adoption of digital assets led the Nigerian market regulators (the SEC specifically) in May 2022 to publish a set of regulations for digital assets, signalling that the country was trying to find a middle ground between an outright ban on digital assets and their potential usage, this was because, before then, sometime in February 2021, the CBN had banned all commercial banks in Nigeria from engaging in any cryptocurrency transaction. This the CBN did in a bid to protect citizens from black market criminal and fraudulent crypto activities. It by the Circular made it clear that the financial system and banking sector of Nigeria would not be linked to cryptocurrency trading – this ban was recently lifted.

As a matter of law, cryptocurrencies are not recognized by the CBN as legal tender¹ yet, despite its increased popularity and an acknowledgement that cryptocurrencies have the

¹ In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria issued a circular in February 2021 stating that cryptocurrencies are not legal tender and advising caution when dealing with them. There is currently no specific tax law regarding cryptocurrencies in Nigeria. However, the Federal Inland Revenue Service has stated that cryptocurrency transactions are taxable as capital gains, this became realisable with the enactment of the Finance Act 2023. This

potential to improve financial inclusion and transparency in the country in the foreseeable future.

Followed by the CBN's ban and amid the growing popularity of cryptocurrencies in the country, the SEC (Nigeria) took on the task to frame a crypto regulation in Nigeria. The Nigerian SEC in May 2022 did this by publishing a comprehensive 54-page document titled "New Rules on Issuance, Offering Platforms and Custody of Digital Assets" on its website.

This document was geared at opening doors for cryptocurrency service providers in Nigeria and a detailed guideline for banking and financial institutions of the country on how they may interact with digital assets, for the major players in Blockchain Technology at the time, this was interpreted as very hostile, as it brought about a number of restrictions and limitations, forcing a number to operate undercover.

The rules also clarified and defined digital assets in Nigeria and iterated that all digital asset token offerings, initial coin offerings and any other blockchain-based offerings within Nigeria or by Nigerian issuers or foreign issuers engaging Nigerian citizens will be regulated by the Nigerian SEC.

Under the Nigerian SEC's new rules, all crypto exchanges providing services in Nigeria are required to secure a licence, which gives the Nigerian SEC access to their records. The digital asset rules, sometimes also commonly referred to as crypto asset rules in Nigeria, further defines a digital asset exchange (DAX) as "an electronic platform that facilitates the trading of a virtual asset or digital asset."

They also clarify a virtual or digital asset as a digital representation of value that has the capability to be used for transfer, trade, payment or investment purposes, thereby bringing cryptocurrencies under its purview.

KEY PLAYERS IN THE WAR

1. THE CENTRAL BANK OF NIGERIA (CBN)

The CBN is Nigeria's central bank and apex monetary authority, originally established by the CBN Act of 1958 (now CBN Act 2007) and became operative from 1st July 1959. The major regulatory objectives of the Bank as stated in the CBN Act are to: ensure monetary and price stability; issue legal tender currency in Nigeria; maintain external reserves to safeguard the international value of the legal tender currency; promote a sound financial system in Nigeria; and act as banker and provide economic and financial advice to the Federal Government.²

In light of these objects, and as already discussed above, the CBN banned banks from crypto-related transactions in 2021, citing money laundering and terrorism financing concerns. It also perceives cryptocurrency transactions to be in conflict

Act aims to tax crypto and digital assets in Nigeria in line with international taxation norms and enhance cross-border growth and regulation for Nigerian citizens and institutions.

² See Section 2, CBN Act

with its role as the issuer of the country's legal tender. However, the regulator has now reversed that ban explaining that current trends globally have shown the need for crypto regulation instead of a total ban.

2. THE SECURITIES AND EXCHANGE COMMISSION (SEC) OF NIGERIA

The Nigerian SEC is an independent government regulatory agency responsible for protecting investors, maintaining fair and orderly functioning of the securities markets, and facilitating capital formation. It is established by the Investments and Securities Act 2007 as the federal regulator of the securities markets. The SEC promotes full public disclosure, protects investors against fraudulent and manipulative practices in the market, and monitors corporate takeover actions in Nigeria. It also approves registration statements for bookrunners among underwriting firms.

Following the launch of \$DAVIDO in June 2024, through Phantom and Solana blockchain channels which quickly gained popularity, reaching a market capitalization of \$10 million in just four hours, SEC, Nigeria has made public a disclaimer to save the general public from investing in it as it was not within its regulatory purview.

An excerpt of its Disclaimer reads,

“The general public is **HEREBY ADVISED** that meme coins lack fundamental value and are purely speculative. The general public is further **WARNED** that investing in meme coins, including \$Davido, is highly risky and should be done with a full understanding of the associated risk.”

3. DIGITAL ASSETS – MEME COINS AS A CASE STUDY

Meme coins are a specie of cryptocurrency, a kind of digital assets. Cryptocurrencies are typically decentralized digital monies designed to be used over the internet, which may better still be called Digital Assets. They are like choses in action, but it appears, are not actionable.

Meme coins are based on memes and online jokes. The difference between them and the other cryptocurrencies is that they are not created based on some innovative technology but on pop culture.

Meme coins started with the creation of the “Dogecoin” by Billy Markus and Jackson Palmer in 2013. After the Dogecoin's success, numerous other meme coins were created, giving us an extensive meme coin list, such as the Shiba Inu, or with its second name, the Dogecoin killer, the Baby DogeCoin or the Dogelon Mars, which is a meme coin that refers to Elon Musk, and the most recent and controversial \$DAVIDO linked to David Adedeji Adeleke (Davido).

How Do Crypto Meme Coins Work?

Crypto meme coins work the same way as traditional cryptocurrencies. They operate on blockchain technology.

Their value comes from their popularity rather than traditional financial metrics. Celebrity mentions on social media can lead to rapid increases or decreases in value. Tweets from figures like Elon Musk have already significantly impacted Dogecoin's price.

It is noteworthy that Meme coins are highly volatile. Their prices can skyrocket or go down quickly or be driven by social media trends and tweets rather than underlying economic factors, making them the perfect investment for investors looking for quick profits based on hype and trend rather than long-term value or utility.

BATTLES AND SKERMISHES – WEAPONS & STRATEGIES OF THE WAR

\$DAVIDO, which was launched with enthusiasm, quickly gained popularity – reaching a market capitalization of \$10 million in just four hours. Using platforms like Phantom and Solana, Davido promoted the coin as a digital tribute to himself, targeting his large social media following.

However, the Nigerian SEC's intervention on Friday, 14th June 2024, raised critical concerns regarding \$DAVIDO's classification and viability as a sound investment. Meme coins, characterized by their origin in internet memes and social media culture, typically lack the underlying value or regulatory oversight associated with traditional investment assets.

The Nigerian SEC clarified that \$DAVIDO does not qualify as a recognized investment product under its regulatory purview, dismissing it as speculative and devoid of fundamental value.

Meme coins like \$DAVIDO are created mostly for fun and community engagement, rather than as serious financial tools. They are not intended for widespread use in purchasing goods or representing traditional investments like stocks or bonds. The Nigerian SEC emphasizes these differences, warning investors to understand the risks before engaging in such a speculative venture.

1. THE PEER TO PEER (P2P) TRANSACTIONS STRATEGY

Peer-to-Peer (P2P) transactions refer to direct exchanges of assets, services, or information between two parties without intermediaries like banks or payment processors. They are empowered by digital platforms and cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin and Ethereum, which use Blockchain technology for transparency and security. It originated with PayPal and have grown rapidly with the advent of smartphone

technology and eliminates intermediaries, leading to faster transactions, reduced fees, and greater autonomy and control for users.

P2P transactions allow individuals to directly transfer funds between one another, bypassing traditional intermediaries like banks. This revolutionary approach has garnered significant attention. Notably, in 2024, it has experienced a growth rate of 9.76% globally, amounting to \$3217.34 million. Its growth trajectory underscores the increasing reliance on P2P services as a preferred mode of financial interaction.

In Africa, Nigeria's growing interest in cryptocurrencies has become noticeable, especially after its mega leap to the forefront during the Crypto Market Crash in April 2022 when a Google Trends data analysis by **CoinGecko** indicated Nigeria to be one of the most crypto-curious nations.

To come up with their report, the search history of various nations was analyzed, and the results emphasized the popularity of cryptocurrencies in Nigeria even amid a crypto dip.

Another report by **Chainalysis** put Nigeria among the top countries showing a high Global Crypto Adoption Index, especially in P2P trading.³

It is believed that such growth in Nigeria is fuelled by inadequate financial services, high inflation, the depreciation of Nigeria's fiat currency (the Naira) and a young demographic (53.7% of Nigeria's population aged 15–65). This tech-savvy Nigerian youth is today yearning for new opportunities for work, investment and financial independence. Blockchain and cryptocurrencies in Nigeria have so far opened doors and presented new financial growth avenues.

This strategy has been the medium by which players in the Blockchain space continue to use to override the schemes of the Government agencies on the lookout for them, hence, avoiding regulations, remaining untraceable and carefully avoiding the tax nets of tax agencies.

2. CIRCULARS AND OTHER REGULATORY ACTIONS

On the other hand, the CBN and SEC, Nigeria, continue to deploy several Regulatory Actions.

In 2021, the CBN released a Circular dated February 5th 2021, ("the Circular") barring commercial banks from engaging in digital assets (this has been discussed above). As a follow-up, the SEC, Nigeria proceeded to put on hold, admittance into its Regulatory Incubation Framework for Fintech Firms, all persons affected by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) cryptocurrencies circular. The Commission disclosed this in a statement it issued in Lagos on Thursday, February 9th, 2021.

³ KuCoin and Paxful are among the leading cryptocurrency exchanges in Nigeria for P2P trading and investing.

It halted the assessment of all persons and products affected by the Circular, and placed their assessment on hold until such persons would be able to operate bank accounts within the Nigerian banking system, hence making their operations regulatable.

This it did to assure investing public that it would continue to monitor developments in the digital asset space to promote economic development. It further engaged all critical stakeholders with a view to creating a regulatory structure that enhanced economic development while promoting a safe, innovative and transparent capital.

The Nigerian SEC has also released a regulation in May 2022, aimed at regulating digital asset management and operations, and more recently, to specifically address \$DAVIDO, a meme coin associated to Davido. It has further described anyone offering crypto or digital asset services as a Virtual Asset Service Provider (VASP), categorized as:

1. DAOPs (Digital Assets Offering Platforms), those that enable digital asset issuance, similar to Initial Coin Offering platforms.
2. DACs (Digital Asset Custodians), who provide safekeeping services for virtual assets, including crypto wallets and exchanges.
3. DAX (Digital Assets Exchanges), which are electronic platforms facilitate the trading of virtual assets, like well-known crypto exchanges such as Binance and Quidax, however many others do not meet up with the licensing arrangements, but yet operate.

Insisting that all such entities go through rigorous licensing hurdles.

Also, The Finance Act 2023, effective from September 2023, is another veritable tool which seeks to amend the Capital Gains Tax (CGT) Act to include 'digital assets' in its scope. These assets are defined as tokens representing debt or equity claims on issuers.

THE BATTLE FIELD – THE NIGERIAN MARKET

As per the SEC's regulation of 2022, DAXs will now need to obtain a virtual asset service provider (VASP) license from the SEC by complying with the requirements of application processing, registration fee and other applicable fees.

Additionally, crypto exchanges are required to provide evidence of a minimum paid-up capital of 500 million naira and a current fidelity bond covering at least 25% of the company's minimum paid-up capital – a sum many existing operators believe they are not capable of affording.

A licensed DAX will be required to abide by the Nigerian SEC regulations and submit an undertaking to ensure the availability of records, ensure personnel and resources availability, security measures, and risk management, and appoint a chief information security officer in order to mitigate cyber risks.

Financial analysts have raised concerns over Davido's newly launched meme coin and warned about the associated risks.

The introduction of the coin into the market has sparked a debate within financial circles.

Experts have highlighted similarities to historical Ponzi schemes, such as MMM, where millions of investors lost substantial amounts of money.

Analysts argued that such coins often capitalise on the popularity of individuals without strong underlying fundamentals or a clear business model.

A financial analyst, Vincent Nwani, stated that if such a coin was allowed to flourish, it would negatively affect the Nigerian financial system. He said,

“To begin with, I'm a huge fan of Davido, his music, and his family, and I will continue to enjoy his tremendous contribution to the Nigerian entertainment industry. Notwithstanding, the recently launched Davido coin is a bit overboard for me because of its semblance to various Ponzi schemes that we have contended with in this economy.”

He noted that Davido's celebrity status and fan base were the primary drivers of the coin's value proposition.

“I say this for so many reasons. First, the workings of the coin seem to be conceived on the strength of Davido's popularity, which he follows with a firm belief that the platform can successfully leverage his brand. If such a coin is allowed to thrive, what it does is that other popular personalities in Nigeria will quickly follow suit, and gross cases of abuse become inevitable. No doubt, this reality has a downside implication for the Nigerian financial system. The MMM experience remains so fresh in our minds. Three million Nigerians lost about N18bn to MMM, and this must not be allowed to happen again.”

The Security Exchange Commission has stated that the meme coin did not get regulatory approval and warned capital market operators not to associate with it.

Another financial analyst, Ambrose Omorodion, advised anyone without financial knowledge to avoid investing in cryptocurrency, adding that the SEC would not take the business to court if investors suffered losses.

“In the financial market, we need more products to fall into. However, meme coins are highly risky and I believe that is why the SEC came out to warn people that they are risky. Also, since cryptocurrency has emerged in the global space, I can see that people are now venturing into it, but my advice is that if they do not have the financial knowledge, they should not go into it or invest at all. The SEC will not sue the company if investors become victims,” he explained.

On the other end, several DAX operators do not comply with the tedious registration requirements for a Nigerian crypto license as a Digital Assets Exchange (DAX) operator, which are: an Application fee of ₦100,000 (\$240); a Processing fee of ₦300,000 (\$722.46); a Registration fee of ₦30 million (\$72,000) and Minimum paid-up capital of ₦500 million (\$1.2 million). Additionally, they must also secure certification from the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) and each exchange must establish a SEC-approved board, and that CEO tenures are limited to ten years, with potential for a five-year extension.

It is also noteworthy that, whilst utilising P2P, traders of these meme coins and other cryptocurrencies do not make funds moved through their bank accounts recognisable as monies used for purchasing digital assets, hence frustrating the Nigerian Capital Gains Taxation system, and the CBN's goal to effectively monitor all such transaction.

VICTORY OR DEFEAT? WHO HAS THE MARKET? – CONCLUSION

Gradually, the Nigerian Government through its financial frontiers has gradually come to believe that these cryptocurrencies, no matter how volatile, are realities that have come to stay.

It can be said that the war has so far been tilting to the victory of Blockchain Technology – Meme Coins inclusive, as the P2P has remained a very strong tool the CBN nor Nigerian SEC could not circumvent, hence, in toeing international practices, the Nigerian Government Nigeria may have to look at the cryptocurrency regulations in Poland and Lithuania where, unlike in Nigeria that imposes substantial financial requirements for crypto exchanges, emphasizing stringent oversight and reporting by the SEC; Poland places a strong emphasis on Anti-Money Laundering (AML) and Know Your Customer (KYC) procedures, along with robust data management and reputation checks; whilst Lithuania's approach operates a system that combines capital requirements with the appointment of local AML officers and local activity mandates, underpinned by lower client identification limits.